

EMERGENCE OF RESEARCH ON ETHNOLINGUISTICS

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Abstract

In this article, the history of the formation of ethnolinguistics in Uzbek and German languages, the work carried out in this regard, the traditions that are part of ethnolinguistics and their role in society are analyzed in detail.

Key words: ethnolinguistics, ethnography, ethnolinguistic materials, candidate theses, ethnographic lexicon, ethnographies, anthropology, sociology, political science, psychology, linguistics.

It is known that A. Doniyorov, one of the researchers of ethnography of Uzbekistan, writes about Uzbek ethnography of the 19th-20th centuries: "It cannot be said that ethnographic works are directed to the interests of state policy, of course. Most of them were prepared for the benefit of the tsarist government. Because the authorities aimed to take over the country and establish themselves here."

Russian scientists and ethnographers went on expeditions to various regions to collect materials related to the lifestyle, customs, and language characteristics of the Turkic peoples. The activity of these expeditions was constantly monitored by the state. For example, according to scientific sources on ethnography, in 1858, the famous Orientalist V.V. Radlov came to Turkestan and published valuable ethnographic information about the inhabitants of the Zarafshan Valley, and based on them, wrote ethnographic pamphlets about local peoples.

The second half of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century are also distinguished by the efforts of local Turkestanists to write generalized ethnographic essays dedicated to individual peoples. For example, N.P. Ostroumov's pamphlet "Sartlar" was published three times. This is an unusual situation for that time, and it testifies to the increasing interest of the readership in the life and household lifestyle of the peoples of Central Asia. Of course, the content of Ostroumov's general essays is dominated by extreme curiosity and approval of his own, because as a pupil of the Kazan Theological Academy, he looked at other non-Russian peoples in a missionary spirit, remaining faithful to the principles of the Kazan Academy.

Thanks to such a movement, a number of works were created that collected the ethnolinguistic materials of the Turkic peoples. Among them, A.N.Samoylovich and P.A.Falev's collection of Crimean-Tatar language proverbs and sayings, and V.P.Nalivkin's and M.V.Nalivkina's work depicting the lifestyle of Fergana Valley women stand out.

At that time, interest in ethnolinguistic materials increased. These interests began to be studied more in the direction of sociolinguistics, and ethnolinguistics developed as a component of sociolinguistics.

Studying the ethnoculture of the ethnic groups that were part of the former empire, the policy of uniting them under a single socialist culture was considered as an object of ethnolinguistics. It was planned that the unification of the ethnic groups located in the territory of the USSR into a single family would be easily realized by eliminating the specific characteristics of each ethnic group and evaluating them as a negative phenomenon. For this reason, the ethnolinguistic process of that time began to be biased.

Under the motto of developing a national, essentially socialist culture, the aim was to unite the cultures of different ethnic groups under the Russian culture and create a single socialist culture on this basis. The words denoting the unique ethnoculture of ethnic groups and their inclusion in the list were considered to be an urgent issue of that time.

"After gaining independence, it became possible to restore our lost values and return them to the people. "Traditions, holidays, rituals and ceremonies that have been trampled on for more than seventy years are being restored, and they are playing an important role in the spiritual revival of the nation, instilling the idea of national independence into the minds of young people."

In Uzbek linguistics, since the 30s of the 20th century, a dictionary of terms representing the ethnoculture of Uzbeks began to appear. In 1933, the linguist scientist U. Tursunov, who was the first to start such research, wrote the first work on Uzbek terminology in the history of Uzbek linguistics and founded the direction of Uzbek terminology. After that, H.T. A number of works by scientists such as Zaripov, S.Ibrohimov, O.Usmanov, M.Mirzayev, I.Rasulov, S.Akobirov, S.Usmanov, devoted to various problems of Uzbek terminology have appeared.

S.Ibrohimov mulberry farming, worm seed preparation, worm catching, cocooning, silk cooking and dyeing, alkalizing, threading, floriculture, weaving, degreasing, knife making, coppersmithing, blacksmithing, blacksmithing, tool making in the Fergana Valley. collected and analyzed rich folk terms related to such fields.

E. Begmatov, a linguist, gave a high assessment to this and expressed his opinion that S. Ibrohimov visited the neighborhoods of the Fergana Valley, collected rich linguistic materials related to his profession, and became the Uzbek Mahmud Kashgari.

In the 1960s and 1970s, a number of scientific works were published in this field. One of such researches is A. Zhoraboyev's candidate's dissertation on the topic "Names of wedding ceremonies in Uzbek". In this source, the existence of traditions of our people with different forms and this situation is the basis for the emergence of a number of names representing these traditions in our language, and their study reveals important theoretical and practical issues of linguistics. it is rightly pointed out that it is of great importance.

Also, the researcher noted that the study of the ethnographic lexicon of the Uzbek literary language and folk dialects is of great importance not only for the science of linguistics, but also for the sciences such as history and ethnography, because these materials are important for people's life, culture and customs at a certain stage of historical development. He said, that it is one of particular importance for a deeper study of what the habits were like. He noted that the ethnographic lexicon is very broad in terms of subject matter and volume. It includes the names of rituals and customs that occur with the birth of a child, circumcision and marriage, hospitality, banquets, public holidays, games and songs, various religious ceremonies, death of a person, as well as other relationships. .

It can be seen that the scope of the ethnographic lexicon is wide, and each of them can be the object of a separate monographic study.

In addition, in Uzbek linguistics, Z. Husainova's "Onomasiological study of the names of wedding ceremonies in the Uzbek language (based on the materials of the Bukhara dialect group)" and F. Hayitova's monographic studies entitled "Linguistic interpretation of wedding songs" are also popular. Some specific aspects of customary names will be covered in detail. The linguist scientist N. Mirzaev has researched more than 1,300 ethnographies in his research entitled "Ethnographic lexicon of the Uzbek language", and in addition, the scientist publishes a large-scale work entitled "Annotated Dictionary of the Ethnography of the Uzbek Language". With this, the scientist contributes to the detailed study of Uzbek ethnographies. Sh. Nurillayeva, who includes her, collects the ethnographies found in Turkestan Qarluq type dialects and analyzes them linguistically.

These studies occupy a special place in the field of research of lexical units representing Uzbek tradition. In these studies, the concepts of traditional lexemes are analyzed within a certain field.

As a result of today's needs, there was a need to cross-examine language units within the framework of two languages. In particular, a special study of the names of lexical expressions related to traditions in the Uzbek and German languages is one of these urgent issues.

British scientist Edward Taylor, one of the founders of ethnography and anthropology, defined culture as "the complex unity of knowledge, belief, art, morality, law, tradition and all other skills and habits acquired by man as a member of society", he described. Communication as a concept of scientific knowledge has a long history and there are several interpretations of it. For example, the American psychologist Jurgen Rüsck noted that there are more than forty interpretations of the concept of communication in such fields as anthropology, sociology, political science, psychology, and linguistics. Therefore, it is natural for specialists from different fields of human activity to collide with communication problems.

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